

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF HYDROTHERMAL CONDITIONS ON GROWTH CHARACTERISTICS AND DEVELOPMENT FOR CEREAL AND CEREAL PEGUM CROPS IN POLISSIA OF UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The grain economy of Ukraine is a strategic and most effective branch of the national economy. Grain and products made from it have always been liquid, as they form the basis of the food base and security of the state. Therefore, the goal was to investigate the influence of hydrothermal conditions on the growth and development of winter wheat, grain sorghum and soybean plants, which ensure the formation of high crop yields. Weather conditions had a significant impact on the duration of the interphase periods of the studied crops. The air temperature and the amount of precipitation had a significant influence, which affected the formation, pouring and ripening of grain crops. High air temperatures and lack of moisture in the soil shortened, and moderately warm and rainy weather extended the grain ripening period. Hot weather and a lack of moisture in the one-meter layer of the soil accelerated the passage of this period for several days, and warm weather and a sufficient amount of moisture increased it.

Keywords: winter wheat, sorghum, soybeans, weather conditions.

Introduction. Currently, Ukraine is one of the most powerful exporters of grain crops to the world market. However, in order to maintain the leading positions, a stable increase in gross grain harvests is necessary.

The grain economy of Ukraine is a strategic and most effective branch for the national economy. Grain and products made from it have always been liquid, as they form the basis for the food base and security for the state [1, 2].

Ukraine, unlike the countries of Western Europe, has opportunities for the development and implementation of organic technologies for growing agricultural crops on large areas. A prerequisite for the development of biological crop production and the production of ecologically clean products is that during the last 10–15 years, farmers, due to a lack of funds, did not use, or used much lower rates of agrochemicals and pesticides. Whereas in the countries of Western Europe at that time up to 350 kg/ha of the active substance of mineral fertilizers were applied [3, 4, 5].

Climate changes have presented humanity with many extremely important and difficult tasks related to the development and implementation of a strategy for its practical existence in such conditions. Based on numerous hydrometeorological indicators, domestic climatologists concluded that a new climate has formed in Ukraine over the past 10–25 years. Winters have become warmer and less snowy, and summers have become cooler. Sometimes there are sharp drops in air temperature – up to 10–12 °C per day. In such periods,

as a rule, there are atmospheric disturbances and natural phenomena, heavy downpours, thunderstorms, hail, wind, etc. [6, 7].

An increase in global temperature by 2–3°C causes permanent economic losses at the level of 0–3 % of global production. With a warming of 5–6 °C, probably in the next century, losses may reach 5–10 % of world GDP. The world is faced with natural anomalies, so it is urgent to join efforts to overcome the consequences of natural disasters, as well as to solve the problems that arise due to global climate change. These changes pose a number of important tasks for Ukraine, in particular, the formation of an appropriate adaptation policy and mitigation of negative consequences [8, 9, 10].

Therefore, the goal was to investigate the influence of hydrothermal conditions on the characteristics of plant growth and development of the studied crops, which ensure the formation of high crop yields.

Materials and methods. Field experiments were conducted during 2020–2022 in the conditions of the educational and research field of the Polissia National University and PE"Chaykivka" (Zhytomyr district, Zhytomyr region). The technology of growing crops in the experiment is generally accepted and recommended for the Polissia zone. The soil of the experimental plots is gray forest light loam.

The meteorological conditions of 2020–2022 were characterized by uneven temperature regime and amount of precipitation during the growing season of crops.

According to hydrothermal conditions, 2021 was unstable and warm. The largest amount of precipitation fell in May, 162.5 mm and was 279.5 % of the norm. However, a moisture deficit and an increase in average daily temperatures were observed in June, July and August, which amounted to 4.0, 12.8 and 63.6 mm, respectively.

The weather conditions of June-August 2022 were characterized by instability: hot days were replaced by cold ones, rainy periods by drought, and in the third decade of July, 117 mm of precipitation fell (303 % of the norm).

Weather conditions determine, first of all, the length of vegetation of plants. Even in the classic works of N. I. Vavilov it is stated that the length of the growing season is determined by many properties of plants and varieties, which depend on the yield, quality for products and the degree for influence of adverse factors.

Results. Currently, negative trends have developed: violation for the frequency for cultivation for agricultural crops in crop rotations and their general rejection, giving preference to the cultivation of business crops and the displacement of leguminous fodder crops; formation for ecologically unfavorable agricultural landscapes with reduction of natural elements; expansion of the scope of application of agrochemicals; growing environmental pressure on the land and environment. Global warming, caused by the increase in greenhouse gas emissions, has led to negative consequences in Ukraine: the production of agricultural products does not even meet the needs of the domestic market; product quality does not always meet world standards; the yield of crops is much lower than in the developed countries of the world; constant growth for anthropogenic load on fertile soils increases the problem of using ecologically safe agriculture [11, 12, 13].

Among the main directions of scientific research in agriculture, the implementation of which will ensure the minimization for greenhouse gas emissions, should include the development of an agricultural system with increased soil protection and moisture-saving functions, focused on the application of contour-reclamation organization of territories with the use of resource-saving technologies and mechanisms: the introduction of adapted to certain soil conditions - climatic conditions of scientifically based crop rotations, which contribute to ecological stabilization and biological balance of the environment and are closely related to the

task of rational use of agricultural landscapes, restoration of fertility, water and nutrient regime of the soil; optimization of the structure of sown areas, due to which land and fertilizers are used more productively, potential opportunities for plant varieties are better realized, weediness is reduced, the effect of pests and diseases in agricultural crops is reduced with minimal use of chemicals; rational use of nitrogen fertilizers by reducing application rates based on their differentiation and more complete use of organic residues, air nitrogen with the use for leguminous crops in accordance with projected climate changes.

One of the important problems that put the world community on the brink of extinction is mass malnutrition and hunger, to one degree or another, it concerns both economically developed and developing countries. Insufficient supply of food has a negative impact on people's life expectancy, their health, physical capacity, adaptation to modern high-tech production processes, etc.

Winter wheat is one of the oldest crops on the globe. Archaeological excavations, all literary data indicate that it was cultivated as early as 5–6 thousand years BC. Wheat is the most important food crop in the world. In terms of cultivated area, it ranks first in the world among agricultural crops. Originating from the Middle East or Western Asia (Iraq, Egypt, China).

The first place in terms of area is occupied by China – 30 million hectares; third place - India – 25.6 million ha. Ukraine is in the top ten – 5.6 million hectares. Of them, up to 90 % of the area is concentrated in the Steppe and Forest Steppe, and about 10 % - in Polissia and the Carpathians [14].

Winter wheat is the main food crop of the country (Fig. 1). The value of wheat bread is determined by the chemical composition of the grain. Among grain crops, it contains the most protein – depending on the variety and growing conditions, its content is 13–15 %. The grain contains a lot of carbohydrates - up to 70 % of starch, vitamins B1, B2, PP, E, provitamins A, D, about 2 % of minerals. Wheat protein is complete in amino acid composition, contains all essential amino acids that are well used by the human body. The ratio of proteins and starch in wheat grains is on average 1:6 – 7, which is the most favorable for maintaining normal body weight and human performance. Wheat bread almost completely provides a person with phosphorus and iron.

Fig. 1. Agrocenosis of winter wheat

In our opinion, a strong argument for the involvement of sorghum in the agrocenoses of Polissia is its extremely high ecological plasticity, capable of being a full-fledged alternative to other warm crops (barley, corn, sunflower, millet) under adverse weather conditions of the growing season.

Sorghum has a special place in solving this problem. Because this crop is the most important fodder, technical and food crop, which occupies a wide area of cultivation all over the world.

Sorghum is a unique cereal crop, both in terms of its biological characteristics and economic characteristics. Its main advantages are exceptional drought resistance, salt tolerance, high productivity, stability of crops over the years, valuable fodder qualities and universal use.

Sorghum is undemanding to soils, it can grow on light and heavy by mechanical composition, with increased salinity, but clean from weeds. In addition, having a powerful root system, it can form high grain yields when grown in monoculture, however, it reacts negatively to cold, swampy and acidic soils (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Agrocenosis of grain sorghum

Leguminous plants occupy an important place among other crops. Soy is especially notable for its con-

tent of various amino acids, B vitamins, calcium, potassium and nutrients that are necessary for the diet of every person (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Agrocenosis of soybeans

Soy is considered an excellent alternative to meat due to its high protein content. Many different dishes can be prepared from this culture, and the main thing is to make oil, butter, milk, flour and other food products.

Benefits of soy consumption: good assimilation and breakdown of protein; its large content; metabolism in the body is accelerated; nerve cells are restored; there is a decrease in cholesterol; normalizes sugar in the body - that is, it can be used for diabetes.

Given the value of soybeans, every year the question of increasing its yield arises, since there are a number of factors that significantly reduce its productivity.

The productivity of agricultural crops, including those under study, is determined by a number of reasons. The volume and quality of the harvest depends on a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors: weather conditions, varietal characteristics of cultivated crops, the state of soil fertility, features of the terrain, the level of intensification of agricultural technologies, etc. As is known, a change in meteorological conditions alone can have a decisive effect on the yield and quality of crop production.

In the system of managing the productive process at the initial stages of plant growth and development, the moisture supply of crops, the temperature regime and the duration of the spring period with the sum of effective temperatures (above +10 °C) are of crucial importance, which significantly affects their development. The temperature determines the rate of swelling, seed germination, the duration of the sowing-seedling period, as well as the timing of the onset of growth phases and the duration of interphase periods throughout the growing season [4].

As a result for research, it was established that the duration of the growing season as a whole and each individual phase of plant development directly depends on growing conditions, moisture supply, air temperature, length of daylight and other factors.

Thus, the duration of the sowing-seedling period depends on the available moisture in the upper layer of the soil. During the years of research, full seedlings appeared 13–15 days after sowing in the soil and depended on the level of moisture.

The duration of the interphase period between seedlings and tillering depended significantly on weather conditions. Thus, the meteorological conditions of this period were contrasting in the amount of precipitation and the temperature regime, while the tillering phase occurred 12–15 days after germination.

The duration of the growing season of crops from full germination to withdrawal into the tube varied by year and was from 22 to 28 days.

One of the most important periods that significantly affects the level of productivity of plants is emergence into the tube. During the years of research, the passage of this period lasted within 10–16 days. The longer this period is, the more plants have the opportunity to develop a good vegetative mass.

Favorable weather conditions during the flowering period - milk ripeness ensure the formation of a sufficient number of grains in the panicle for the formation of a future high harvest. The duration of the interphase period was 20–24 days.

However, it should be noted that an increase in the duration of the milk-wax maturity period causes a decrease in the yield. Thus, excessive precipitation can cause an increase in the duration of this period, which leads to crop losses and deterioration of its quality. Also, the level of the crop is affected by the increased air temperatures under which thin grain is formed.

Conclusion. Therefore, weather conditions had a significant impact on the duration of interphase periods. The air temperature and the amount of precipitation had a significant influence, which affected the formation, pouring and ripening of grain crops. High air temperatures and lack of moisture in the soil shortened, and moderately warm and rainy weather extended the grain ripening period. Hot weather and a lack of moisture in the one-meter layer of the soil accelerated the passage of this period for several days, and warm weather and a sufficient amount of moisture increased it. Thus, the development of the studied crops was determined by the influence of abiotic factors during the growing season.

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